

A LITERATURE REVIEW ON INTERVENTIONS FOR POST-TRAUMATIC STRESS DISORDER (PTSD) IN DOMESTIC VIOLENCE VICTIMS

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Abstract

Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD) is a psychological condition that arises as a result of traumatic events and is characterized by symptoms such as nightmares, flashbacks, avoidance behaviors, and hyperarousal. PTSD is commonly experienced by survivors of domestic violence, particularly those subjected to repeated physical, emotional, or sexual abuse. This study presents a literature review aimed at exploring current understandings of PTSD among domestic violence survivors, focusing on risk factors, symptoms, diagnosis, and treatment approaches. The method employed was a rapid review of ten journal articles published between 2020 and 2023, sourced from both Indonesian and international journals via sage journals, science direct, and google scholar. The findings of this review are expected to provide a comprehensive overview of recent advancements and to propose more effective intervention strategies for survivors of domestic violence. A total of eight articles were identified as meeting the inclusion criteria and aligning with the objectives of this study. Evidence-based treatment approaches for addressing post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) in this population include cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT), exposure therapy, group therapy, and mindfulness-based interventions.

Keywords: Emotional Violence, Female Survivors, Trauma, Post-Traumatic Stress.

1. INTRODUCTION

Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD) is a psychological reaction that arises from a traumatic event that threatens life or causes unpleasant feelings or stress (1)(2)(3). This condition is characterized by feelings of sadness, depression, and a lack of enthusiasm for performing daily activities or activities that bring pleasure. It is sometimes accompanied by delusions, and when severe, can disrupt role functioning and social life (4)(5). DSM-IV outlines the diagnostic criteria for PTSD as symptoms of re-experiencing, such as nightmares or flashbacks, avoidance, and hyperarousal, including anger, sleep disturbances, and panic that last for more than a month. Grinage (2003) stated that patients with PTSD symptoms often display excessive reactions due to neurobiological changes in the nervous system. Only a small portion of the brain is responsible for speech and language comprehension (Broca's area), while other parts of the brain primarily respond to panic symptoms, flashbacks, startled reactions, and feelings of tightness in the neck and throat (amygdala, thalamus, hippocampus, anterior cingulate gyrus). PTSD is a complex mental health disorder that can affect individuals who have experienced or witnessed traumatic events, from natural disasters to interpersonal violence or armed conflict. Research on PTSD has become increasingly important as awareness of mental health grows.(6)

A study revealed that approximately 40 to 60% of female survivors of domestic violence experience post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD)(7), characterized primarily by symptoms such as hypervigilance, traumatic flashbacks, and avoidance of situations that trigger memories of the abuse. Domestic Violence (DV) is one form of interpersonal violence that can cause deep trauma to its victims. Domestic violence victims often experience PTSD as a result of repeated exposure to physical, emotional, or sexual abuse. The long-term impact of domestic violence on the mental health of victims is significant, requiring special attention in their treatment and recovery. This literature review aims to explore the latest understanding of PTSD in domestic violence victims,

including risk factors, symptoms, diagnosis, and the most effective treatment approaches. By understanding the dynamics of PTSD in the context of domestic violence, it is hoped that better intervention strategies can be developed to help victims recover and rebuild their lives.(8)

2. METHODOLOGY

This literature review employed a rapid review methodology to efficiently synthesize the most recent and pertinent research on post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) resulting from sexual violence within domestic settings. The literature search was conducted via sage journals, science direct and google scholar, encompassing Indonesian journals, nationally accredited publications, and internationally recognized peer-reviewed journals. The inclusion criteria were as follows: articles published between 2020 and 2025; peer-reviewed studies focusing on PTSD in the context of sexual violence; and articles available in full text, written in either English or Indonesian. A total of eight relevant journal articles were selected based on their alignment with the study's objectives. Keyword combinations such as "PTSD," "sexual violence," "domestic violence survivors," and "mental health intervention" were utilized alongside publication year filters to ensure the inclusion of up-to-date findings(9).

To synthesize the selected articles, a thematic analysis approach was applied. Each article was reviewed in depth to identify recurring themes, patterns, and intervention strategies. Key data such as research objectives, sample characteristics, methodology, major findings, and conclusions were extracted and categorized. This process allowed for comparison across studies, highlighting both consistent findings and areas of divergence. The synthesized data were then grouped under thematic categories related to types of intervention, psychological outcomes, and cultural or contextual influences on PTSD treatment efficacy(10). This methodological approach ensured a structured and systematic integration of findings, providing a comprehensive and current overview of PTSD intervention strategies for survivors of sexual violence in domestic contexts.

3. RESULTS

A rapid review of nine relevant studies on PTSD in survivors of domestic violence (DV) reveals a variety of therapeutic interventions, symptom profiles, and psychosocial impacts associated with PTSD, particularly as it relates to sexual violence. The findings from each study provide valuable insights into the effectiveness of different therapeutic approaches for survivors of domestic violence. Below is a summary of the key findings from each of the studies included in the review:

No	Title	Aim	Metohod	Result
1	Self Talk dan Guided Imagery dalam Penanganan Stress Pasca Trauma Kekerasan dalam Rumah Tangga. Aini AN, Dona S, Mahdiyah D. Heal Res J Indones. 2023;1(4):172–8.	To examine the effectiveness of self-talk and guided imagery techniques as psychological interventions in managing PTSD symptoms among survivors of domestic violence	Quasi-experimental	"Self-Talk and Guided Imagery in Managing Post-Traumatic Stress Following Domestic Violence" examined the use of positive self-talk and guided imagery as therapeutic interventions for DV survivors with PTSD. Results indicated that participants who received both self-talk and guided imagery

				experienced a significant reduction in PTSD symptoms compared to the control group, which only received self-talk. Positive self-talk fostered optimistic thought patterns, while guided imagery, especially nature-based imagery, was more effective in reducing anxiety than urban-themed imagery(11).
2	Pengurangan simptom post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) terhadap restrukturisasi kognitif media Surat Al-fatihah pada korban KDRT. Dwi S. J Ris Psikol. 2023;6(1):53–62.	To assess the effectiveness of cognitive restructuring using the media of Surah Al-Fatihah in reducing PTSD symptoms among survivors of domestic violence.	One-group pretest-posttest design, quasi-experimental	This study explored the use of cognitive restructuring through reflection on Surah Al-Fatihah in reducing PTSD symptoms among DV survivors. The results showed a significant reduction in PTSD symptoms, with participants shifting from severe to mild symptoms following the intervention. This approach not only helped reduce PTSD symptoms but also improved the adaptability of participants' behaviors and thoughts, providing a spiritually-based intervention for trauma recovery(12).
3	Pengaruh Terapi Observed	This study was to examine the	Single-case experiment	The OEI therapy provided a safe and deep space

	Experiential Integration Untuk Menurunkan Gejala Post Traumatic Stress Disorder Pada Wanita Korban Perkosaan. Abimanyu CVR. Semarang; 2015.	effectiveness of Observed Experiential Integration (OEI) therapy in reducing post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) symptoms among women survivors of sexual assault. The study sought to determine whether OEI could alleviate trauma-related stress and enhance emotional regulation in this population.	al design with a multiple baseline design across three participants .	for female survivors of DV to express and process their traumatic experiences. The study found significant reductions in PTSD symptoms, including intrusion, avoidance, and hyperarousal. The OEI therapeutic process, involving phases such as Switching, Glitch Work, and Sweeping, enabled participants to access cognitive processing and engage in a safe environment for emotional expression (13).
4	Metode Hipnoterapi dalam Menangani Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD) Pada Perempuan Korban Kekerasan dalam Rumah Tangga di DP3AP2KB Provinsi Jawa Tengah. Rahmawati NF, Kholilurrohman K. J Kesehatan. 2023;4.	This study was to evaluate the effectiveness of hypnotherapy in reducing PTSD symptoms among women survivors of domestic violence.	Qualitative approach with a descriptive method	Participants who underwent hypnotherapy reported positive outcomes, including increased happiness, calmness, and the ability to cope with life more effectively. The results suggest that hypnotherapy effectively alleviates PTSD symptoms by helping individuals resolve past trauma, leading to enhanced emotional well-being and overall life satisfaction (14).
5	Konseling CBT untuk	To assess the effectiveness of	Experiment al design	This study demonstrated that CBT, in a group

	Mengembangkan Self-love Penyintas Trauma Kekerasan Dalam Rumah Tangga (KDRT). Krisnanda VD, Ramli M, Hidayah N. Couns J Bimbing dan Konseling. 2022;12(2):116–29.	Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (CBT) counseling in developing self-love among survivors of domestic violence trauma		counseling format, helped female DV survivors improve self-love. By addressing cognitive distortions and promoting relaxation techniques, CBT helped participants reduce PTSD symptoms and improve their quality of life. However, challenges such as limited therapy time and trauma reactivation during sessions were noted. Despite these challenges, CBT was recommended as an effective therapeutic intervention for survivors (15).
6	Efektivitas terapi zikir istighfar untuk mengurangi gejala gangguan stres pascatrauma pada istri korban kekerasan dalam rumah tangga. Kartikasari M, Nashori F. Psychopolytan J Psikol. 2022;5(2):83–98.	To assess the effectiveness of Istighfar-based dhikr therapy in reducing post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) symptoms among wives who are victims of domestic violence. The study sought to determine whether this spiritual intervention could alleviate trauma-related stress and enhance emotional regulation in this population.	Mixed-methods design (quantitative+qualitative) with a quasi-experimental approach	The use of Dzikir Istighfar (Islamic prayer) as a therapeutic intervention resulted in significant reductions in PTSD symptoms. Participants reported increased inner peace, self-awareness regarding past mistakes, and greater control over PTSD symptoms. This study supports the notion that spiritual practices, such as Dzikir Istighfar, can provide emotional support and foster positive self-transformation in the face of trauma (16).

7	<p>Recovery: Resilience and growth in the aftermath of domestic violence. Violence Against Women. Anderson KM, Renner LM, Danis FS. 2012;18(11):1279–99.</p>	<p>The primary aim of this study was to explore the recovery process and outcomes for women who had previously been in abusive intimate partner relationships</p>	<p>Mixed-methods study mixed-methods study</p>	<p>This study highlighted the recovery process of women who had left abusive relationships. Many women demonstrated strong resilience and low levels of PTSD symptoms even years after experiencing prolonged DV. The research emphasized the role of spiritual and social support in healing and growth post-abuse. Despite resilience, some women continued to face challenges in decision-making and trauma-related symptoms, indicating the complex nature of recovery from domestic violence (17).</p>
8	<p>Post-traumatic growth among domestic violence survivors: A systematic. Rahayu D, Hamidah H, Hendriani W. review. J Educ Heal Community Psychol. 2019;8(2):138–58.</p>	<p>To examine how previous empirical studies explain the struggles experienced by victims of domestic violence, the strategies employed to address their traumatic conditions, and the factors contributing to positive changes, specifically post-traumatic growth (PTG)</p>	<p>Systematic review</p>	<p>A study conducted by Zunea Farizka Azyza Harro Uasni explored post-traumatic growth (PTG) in DV survivors, revealing that many women experienced significant positive changes as a result of their struggle with trauma. Factors such as social support, emotional disclosure, and spirituality were identified as key contributors to PTG. Despite the trauma,</p>

				women exhibited improvements in life appreciation, relationships, personal strength, spirituality, and new possibilities for the future (9) .
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4. DISCUSSION

The findings from these studies reveal a range of therapeutic approaches that effectively address PTSD in survivors of domestic violence. These include psychological interventions, spiritual approaches, and experiential therapies that highlight the potential for comprehensive trauma recovery. Below is a discussion of the key themes and implications of the findings:

a. Self-Talk and Guided Imagery

Research by Aini, Dona, and Mahdiyah (2023)(11), supports the use of these techniques as they promote cognitive restructuring and emotional regulation, critical components for trauma recovery. Additionally, guided imagery helps in activating the parasympathetic nervous system, reducing physiological symptoms of anxiety and promoting a sense of calm. Self-talk and guided imagery also contribute to enhancing survivors' self-efficacy and internal locus of control, important factors for restoring personal agency and empowerment after trauma(18). These interventions are adaptable to both individual and group therapy settings, making them versatile in clinical practice. In addition to symptom management, these cognitive-behavioral tools have been associated with fostering post-traumatic growth and resilience, helping survivors rebuild positive self-identity and coping mechanisms(18). Integrating these methods with complementary approaches such as mindfulness or exposure therapy can offer comprehensive care tailored to survivors' needs.

b. Cognitive Restructuring with Surah Al-Fatihah

The use of cognitive restructuring with spiritual reflection on Surah Al-Fatihah demonstrated its potential in not only reducing PTSD symptoms but also improving behavioral adaptability and promoting spiritual healing. This approach underscores the therapeutic value of integrating spiritual and cognitive interventions, which can be a culturally relevant and effective strategy for DV survivors seeking healing (19),(20).

A study by Dwi (2023) demonstrated that cognitive restructuring through Surah Al-Fatihah reflection significantly decreased PTSD symptoms among DV survivors. By engaging in *tadabbur*—a reflective contemplation of the verses—participants experienced a transformation in dysfunctional self-beliefs into more adaptive and spiritually anchored self-perceptions, resulting in the reduction of PTSD severity from “severe” to “mild” (12). Supporting this, Singgih and Triana (2023) introduced the Al-Fatihah Reflection Therapy (ART) model, which successfully enhanced resilience among individuals with disabilities. The model integrates Quranic reflection with cognitive behavioral elements, focusing on modifying maladaptive thoughts and emotions through structured spiritual engagement (21).

Similarly, Luthfiyah et al. (2023) found that guided spiritual reflection on Surah Al-Fatihah was effective in alleviating anxiety among university students. The practice of reading and internalizing the meanings of the Surah fostered a sense of calm, trust in divine will, and emotional regulation, thus serving as a preventive mental health strategy (22).

Collectively, these studies support the growing evidence base for spiritually-informed psychological care. The integration of Surah Al-Fatihah into cognitive restructuring provides not only a means to reduce PTSD symptoms but also fosters post-traumatic growth, purpose reconstruction, and spiritual resilience in survivors of domestic violence.

c. Observed & Experiential Integration (OEI)

The OEI therapy offers a holistic and experiential therapeutic approach, helping survivors process trauma in a safe environment. The findings indicate that OEI significantly reduces PTSD symptoms by fostering emotional expression and cognitive processing. This approach is valuable in trauma recovery as it promotes deep emotional healing and cognitive reframing in a supportive environment (23),(24).

A study by Bradshaw et al. (2014) demonstrated that OEI therapy effectively reduced PTSD symptoms in a diverse group of trauma survivors. The randomized clinical trial revealed that 90% of participants experienced significant relief from PTSD symptoms, as indicated by the Clinician-Administered PTSD Scale (CAPS) and the Impact of Event Scale-Revised (IES-R) scores. The intervention consisted of three one-hour sessions using a single technique known as 'switching,' which involves alternating eye coverage to stimulate different visual pathways connected to the brain's hemispheres. The study found that OEI therapy outperformed the delayed-treatment control condition in reducing PTSD symptoms, with sustained benefits observed in a two-year follow-up (25).

Additionally, research by Anggadewi (2023) focused on the application of OEI therapy in reducing PTSD symptoms among female survivors of domestic violence. The study found that OEI therapy led to a significant decrease in PTSD symptoms, highlighting its effectiveness in addressing trauma within this specific population (26).

Furthermore, OEI therapy's emphasis on emotional processing aligns with findings from other therapeutic modalities. For instance, a study examining prolonged exposure therapy for PTSD found that emotional processing, particularly the reduction of negative trauma-related cognitions and cognitive rigidity, was a key predictor of symptom improvement. This underscores the importance of emotional expression and cognitive processing in trauma recovery. ScienceDirect

In conclusion, OEI therapy provides a valuable intervention for trauma recovery by integrating emotional expression and cognitive processing in a supportive environment. Its application among survivors of domestic violence demonstrates its potential in reducing PTSD symptoms and promoting healing.

d. Hypnotherapy

Hypnotherapy proved effective in reducing PTSD symptoms, enabling survivors to resolve past trauma and enhance their emotional well-being. The study suggests that hypnotherapy can be an important tool in trauma recovery, especially for those who may struggle to engage with traditional therapeutic approaches. It highlights the need for diverse therapeutic options to meet the varied needs of DV survivors (27). Collectively, these studies reinforce the efficacy of hypnotherapy in alleviating PTSD symptoms among trauma survivors, including those who have experienced domestic violence. Hypnotherapy offers a valuable therapeutic option, particularly for individuals who may find traditional therapeutic approaches challenging. Its ability to facilitate emotional processing and cognitive reframing in a supportive environment makes it a promising tool in trauma recovery.

e. Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (CBT)

CBT was shown to be highly effective in improving self-love and reducing PTSD symptoms in DV survivors. However, challenges such as limited time and reactivation of trauma during therapy were identified. Despite these challenges, CBT remains a promising therapeutic approach for helping survivors rebuild their sense of self-worth and manage trauma-related symptoms effectively (28),(29).

A study by Krisnanda et al. (2022) focused on using CBT-based counseling to enhance self-love among DV survivors with trauma. The research demonstrated significant improvements in self-compassion and reductions in PTSD symptoms after a series of CBT sessions, highlighting the therapy's capacity to rebuild survivors' self-worth and emotional resilience (15). However, challenges were noted in clinical practice. Time constraints limited the number of therapy sessions, sometimes hindering full trauma processing. Additionally, reactivation of traumatic memories during exposure or cognitive restructuring occasionally caused emotional distress, requiring careful therapist guidance to prevent dropout or symptom exacerbation(30). Despite these hurdles, CBT remains a frontline intervention due to its evidence base and adaptability.(31)

CBT significantly reduced PTSD symptom severity in women survivors of intimate partner violence, while improving emotional regulation and self-esteem. The study emphasized the importance of trauma-informed adaptations to address therapy-related distress and increase retention(32). CBT is one of the most effective interventions for PTSD in survivors of interpersonal violence, promoting cognitive restructuring that enhances self-perception and reduces symptoms such as avoidance and hypervigilance.

f. Dzikir Istighfar (Islamic Prayer)

Research highlights that integrating spiritual practices such as prayer, meditation, and recitations into trauma recovery frameworks not only addresses the psychological aspects of PTSD but also meets the spiritual and cultural needs of survivors. This holistic approach promotes a sense of meaning, hope, and connectedness, which are critical components in the healing process. Dzikir Istighfar, as a form of spiritual therapy, was found to significantly alleviate PTSD symptoms. The therapeutic benefits of spiritual practices such as prayer underscore the importance of integrating spiritual support in trauma recovery. This finding highlights the potential of spiritual-based therapies in addressing trauma, especially in culturally and religiously specific contexts (33). Kartikasari and Nashori (2022) conducted a study investigating the effectiveness of Dzikir Istighfar therapy in reducing PTSD symptoms among wives of domestic violence survivors. The study found significant reductions in symptoms such as hyperarousal, flashbacks, and emotional distress following a structured Dzikir Istighfar intervention, confirming the therapy's potential as a culturally congruent healing modality(34).

g. Post-Traumatic Growth (PTG)

The concept of post-traumatic growth (PTG) demonstrates that, despite experiencing severe trauma, DV survivors can experience significant positive changes in their lives. Factors such as social support, emotional disclosure, and spirituality were found to contribute to PTG, suggesting that recovery is not merely about symptom reduction but also involves personal growth and transformation (35),(9).

These studies demonstrate that recovery from domestic violence extends beyond symptom reduction and involves significant personal transformation. Key factors including social support, emotional disclosure, and spirituality have been shown to facilitate post-traumatic growth among survivors. Therefore, recovery approaches should integrate therapeutic interventions with psychosocial support systems that promote growth and transformation after trauma.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The findings from this review suggest that a wide range of therapeutic interventions, including cognitive-behavioral techniques, spiritual therapies, and experiential therapies, can effectively address PTSD in survivors of domestic violence. The integration of spiritual and cognitive interventions appears to be particularly beneficial, offering survivors a multifaceted approach to recovery. Furthermore, these studies highlight the importance of social support, spirituality, and individual resilience in the healing process. Future research should continue to explore these interventions in greater depth, especially through larger and more diverse samples, to enhance our understanding of how best to support DV survivors in their recovery journeys. Get smarter responses, upload files and images, and more.

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